

EIT Community New European Bauhaus

FISHART

FINAL ACTIVITY REPORTING

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Project ID: 240006 FishArt
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Project website: <https://crowdusg.net/fishart/>

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1. Executive summary

PROJECT INSIGHTS

WHAT IS “FISHART: PARTICIPATORY ART FOR THE OCEAN”?

FishArt is a 10-month international project funded by the New European Bauhaus Cross-KIC Connect 2024 written by and granted to Chiara Certoma' (UniTo – now at UniRm1) and led by Laura Corazza (UniTo), in collaboration with Raw-News, Platoon and the fishermen cooperatives of Anzio (Rome, Italy). FishArt promotes a radically participatory art and education process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy. It raises awareness and public acceptance of sustainable behaviours against marine and coastal pollution and promotes the synergic and co-creative transformation of a functional but degraded public

space into a place for community life. Building upon the local ecosystem analysis, the wide social network and the results of the recent EU project “SeaPaCS”, FishArt envisages multistakeholder workshops with target groups (fishermen and artists cooperatives) and local stakeholders (administrations, students, associations, migrants, seagoing people, businesses and enterprises, scientists); multidisciplinary (social geography, oceanography, communication) and multi-sectorial (fisherman, artists, businesses) learning sessions; a Living Lab for co-design and realisation of artistic works and a final FishArt Event.

[photo G.Lupinacci/Raw-News for SeaPaCS]

2. Overall progress of the project

2.1. Brief description of the activity, main challenges

Participatory Art for environmental sustainability and aesthetic transformation of Anzio Fishermen's Harbour

FishArt aims to support and complement infrastructural requalification processes of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio (50,000 in., 60 km South of Rome, Italy) undertaken by the Local Administration via the realisation of a marine litter collection area.

The FishArt participatory aesthetic and cultural transformation of the area is intended to revitalise a public space, functional for the local economy and closely connected with coastal waters, from the current state of dumping and degradation.

The 1km-long Fishermen's Harbour is located in the city centre and is used for

the unloading of fishing boats and the retail sale of fish. Although it offers a wonderful walk about the sea, it is not frequented by citizens because of the marine and fishing wastes abandoned on the quay. By request of fishermen cooperatives, galvanised by the success of the EU project "SeaPaCS – Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution" (led by UniTo in Anzio in 2023), FishArt intends to produce participatory cultural and art installations and performances in the Harbour.

The cultural revival of the Harbour is intended as a trigger for collective engagement toward sustainability and a bulwark against abandonment.

2. Overall progress of the project

2.2. Methodology of the engagement with local stakeholders and the co-design process

The Fishermen's Harbour is a crucial economic and social area, with many seagoing professionals and business people operating there, as local economy is highly dependent on the sea (fishing, commercial boating, and tourism). Nevertheless the disregard for public goods and space brought a progressive and severe degradation of the area, aggravated by the presence of corruption in the waste management sector. The project offers the opportunity to bootstrap local efforts for a revitalising marine and public culture and connect it at the international level. Moreover, coastal and functional public spaces are often neglected and at risk of vandalization and deterioration.

This is particularly detrimental for both those people who frequent them on a daily basis for their work, such as seagoing professionals, and the citizens at large. Coastal and maritime public space, when derelict, are also characterised by visible pollution which easily reverse into the sea further affecting the already compromised health of our seas and the coastal water. To contrast this trend, target groups involved are innovatively experimenting with the dialogue between fishermen cooperatives and artists societies to fostering a sense of community, attachment and care for the sea and the local community.

2. Overall progress of the project

2.3. Work plan of the activities

[T.= task, m= months, sup.= support,
M=milestones, Ob=objective, D=deliverables,
O=Outcome, Outputs=Ou]

- **T. 01** Activity Management [UniTo] (Ob1, m.1-10, CL01). Set up administrative, managerial, ethical compliance, risk and data management procedures. D: Management plans O:A-C Ou:2
- **T. 02** Management of communication, networking and dissemination [UniTo, sup: media-agency] (Ob3-5, m.1-10, CL01). Set up and maintenance of web page, social media, mailing list; networking local stakeholders+target groups (fishermen and artists) and international experts, in-site communication; media contacts; photo and video documentation; scientific paper elaboration. D: 1 web page, 6 newsletters, 6 press realises, 1 scientific paper, 2 photo exhibitions (25 professional pictures) and 3 professional videos (2/3 mins), 6 YouTube videos. O:C Ou:1
- **T. 03** Fist workshop [UniTo, sup: LNI] (Ob3-4, m.2, EITHE08.1). Kick-off plenary open meeting with local stakeholders and administration for process design,

issue discussion, preparation and logistics for T.4 and T.5. M: FishArt local stakeholder community engaged and Implementation designed plan approved D:1 Plan for the future Harbour, Financial plan for T.3-6 O:A, B Ou:2

- **T. 04** Participatory education and training initiatives [UniTo, sup: external experts] (Ob3-4, m.3-6, EITHE08.1). Preparation and realisation of collaborative education on tacit and transformative local knowledge open to all citizens (1. Transect walk with fishermen at the harbour 2. Researchers presenting the challenges for the global ocean and local area, 3. Public meeting with local schools presenting works on the society's attachment to the sea in Anzio and marine waste.Beachhead Cleanup "Let´s not make war, Let´s fight waste!" M: Matchmaking and cross-fertilisation phase for identify main challenges realised D: 1 intermediate report, 3 co-training events O:A Ou:2
- **Task 05** FishArt Living Lab and Event [UniTo, sup: Fishermen coops, Platoon, Local Admin.] (Ob2&4, m.5-10, CL01). Creation of a temporary living lab with target groups and ideation of 22 artistic

performances/installations, focused on marine and coastal area pollution, to be realised in the Harbour; design of the collaborative art process (involving stakeholders) and preparation of artworks (including logistic, materials and practical organisation); exhibition/exposition of the artworks during a FishArt Event at the Harbour M. Regular LL meetings and artworks practicalities arranged D. 3 artworks plan and realisation, 1 FishArt Event O:B Ou:1

- **Task 06** Second workshops [UniTo] (Ob4, m.10, CL01). Plenary open meeting for results presentations, activity assessment (stakeholder survey), and design of follow-up (scaling-up and sustainability) plan. M. all communication product ready, stakeholders' engagement in follow-up plan D. 1 final report including assessment and follow-up plan. O:A, B Ou:2

2. Overall progress of the project

2.4. Achievement of the objectives

ACHIEVEMENTS

PROJECT TIMELINE

PROJECT ACTIVITY: FEBRUARY - JUNE

1. DELX • L.A.D.I. (is) in the Sea! From SeaPaCS to FishArt
2. 26.02 • DEL09 • Feeling the Ocean. Cfp RGS 2024 on co-creative science+art+activism experimentations.
3. 06.02 • DEL01: FishArt kick-off meeting
4. 19.02 • DEL01: FishArt Living Lab: Activity Management [PROJECT DIARY](#)
5. 06.03 • DEL08: FishArt Newsletter Campaigns Web Communication Products
6. 21.03 • DEL05: FishArt_First Collaboratorium #1
7. 12.04 • DEL10: “Plastisphere Explorations. Submarine plots of nature-culture” Geography Night
8. 08.05 • DEL06: FishArt Event: Call for Collaboration & Artwork Creation
9. 10.05 • DEL05: FishArtLiving Lab #1: “Let’s not wage war, let’s fight waste”
10. 11.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab #2: Tentacular Thinking Operative Meeting Berlin
11. 13.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab: EU NEB COHORT SESSIONS
12. 15.05 • DEL06: PARTICIPATORY ART PROGRAM
13. 21.05 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab: Mentorship program
14. 12.06 • DEL07: FishArt Event: Site Inspection
15. 20.06 • DEL08: FISHART EVENT COMMUNICATION & DESIGN
16. 28.06 • DEL01: MEETINGS & WORK SESSIONS
17. 29.06 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab #3: Participants Meetup
18. 30.06 • DEL04: Mid-Term Report

DEL EXTRA • L.A.D.I. (is) in the Sea! From SeaPaCS to FishArt

On the 4th and 30th of April, and 24th May kids and teachers of the Sailing School organised by the Italian Naval League Anzio operatively kicked off the SeaPaCS spin-off project “L.A.D.I. and the Sea”, anticipated by the inaugural presentation during the final collaboratorium of the SeaPaCS project (LIN) in November 2023,) to monitor plastic debris along the coast of Anzio (Rome, Italy).

The “L.A.D.I. and the Sea” has been supported by the University of Turin – ESOMAS Department and the Italian Naval League of Anzio, in collaboration with dr. Luisa Galgani and Nicola Gaggelli, University of Siena – Chemistry Dep. which will take care of the analysis of the collected sample to determine what kind of plastic are collected in the local sea by producing a short time series of data. Students of the local schools are involved in sampling

microplastics using a special self-built sampling network during SeaPaCS, called L.A.D.I. (Low-tech Aquatic Debris Instrument) built by volunteer citizen Giuseppe Certomà and gifted to the LNI for teaching activity and tested in august 2023. A further L.A.D.I. is expected to be built up and offered by of the Rotary Club Costa Neroniana. On the occasion of the starting of the “L.A.D.I. and the Sea”, the sport director of the Italian Naval League Anzio, Federico Fornaro, presented to participating schools the EU NEB project “FishArt. Participatory Art for the ocean at Anzio Fishermen’s Harbour” and invited kids to participate in the planned events. During the day the participatory and open education initiative envisaged from the workplan to engage and collect insights from the youngest

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

DEL09 • Feeling the Ocean. Cfp RGS 2024 on co-creative science+art+activism experimentations.

More details on the conference, including the open call for papers, are available [here](#).

We invite abstracts for the Royal Geographical Conference 2024 in London on the following session topic. The session is sponsored by the Coastal and Maritime Research Group. The session is co-organised and chaired by Chiara Certoma (University of Rome La Sapienza), Federico Fornaro (Raw-News), Stefania Benetti (University of Eastern Piedmont), Antonella Passani (T6-Ecosystem)

The session focuses on how the combination of science, art and participatory processes can contribute to exploring and establishing a connection between society and the ocean. Our interest goes to transectorial and transdisciplinary-inspired artistic and creative processes promoted by scientists,

artists, activists, seagoing people and ocean-lovers that experiment with new forms of investigation and expression to explore to motivate, trigger and support our commitments toward ocean challenges. Particularly we focus on participatory or collaborative artistic and creative processes on the belief that that engagement can bring about a deeper understanding and commitment of society with ocean hazards and challenges, not only via cultural consumption, but also in experimenting with artistic/performing arts themselves.

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

DEL01 • FishArt kick-off meeting

The kick-off meeting of the of the EU NEB FishArt project is held on the 26th of February at the Municipality of Anzio, Rome (Italy) with representatives of the administration and the Capitaneria di Porto.

FishArt promotes a radically participatory art and education process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy.

During the kick-off meeting with dr. Monaco, Anzio City Council and mar. Costabile, Capitaneria di Porto, the project inspiration, the programme and the logistic details have been discussed. [FULL ARTICLE](#)

The project presentation by Chiara Certomà is available [here](#)

DEL01 • FishArt Living Lab: Activity Management

06.02.2024 Project set-up meeting with NEB project officer FishArt team with UniTo secretary and NEB PO (Ellen Gale)

19.02.2024 Operative meeting FishArt team

26.02.2024 FishArt Kick-off meeting with local administration (Eugenio Monaco) and harbour institution (Massimo Costabile)

05.04.2024 Starting of the mentorship programme with NEB PO (Ellen Gale) and Vanessa Gerotto

DEL05 #1 • FishArt_First Collaboratorium

On March 21, 2024, the first public FishArt collaboratory is held at the Italian Naval League in Anzio (Rome, Italy) with local stakeholders at 6 pm. Promoters Chiara Certomà (University of Turin and Rome Sapienza), Federico Fornaro, director of the international video documentation company Raw-News and Marcello Dato connected from Berlin for the international artistic promotion company Platoon welcomed the participants and presented the activities envisaged by the FishArt project aimed at supporting the sustainable redevelopment process of the port area of Anzio undertaken by the Local Administration. Through the active participation of all components of the local population, and in connection with international experiences and experts, co-education initiatives will be implemented for the protection of the ocean from pollution and the revitalisation of public space with artistic and creative events.

Participants were invited to participate in the planned events, in particular the first co-education event “Non Facciamo la guerra, Combattiamo i Rifiuti”(2 May 2024) organised by Municipality of Anzio in collaboration with the FishArt project,

the FishArt Living Lab meeting (May-June) for the collective planning of the FishArt Event (July) which involves the creation, implementation and installation in the port areas for the Ocean of moments creative and artistic works (about which invitations and information will be sent in time).

Furthermore at the end of the collaboratorium, the DUWO boxes, washable and reusable, are delivered to the captains of the remaining 10 fishing boats of the “Concordia” and “Fanciulla d’Anzio” Cooperative of Anzio-Roma at the Innocenziano Pier, after the European project “SeaPaCS. Citizen-Scientist against plastic in the sea”. (<https://crowdusg.net/seapacs/>).

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

[VIDEO REPORT](#) (Long Version)

[cover photo G.Lupinacci]

DEL05 #2 • FishArt Living Lab #1: Planning & Production

01.04-02.025.2024 Living Lab activity #1:
coordination, logistical and technical organization, networking, institutional requirements and realisation of the community plogging event by Raw-News, Raw-Drivers and Platoon with Municipal Administration (Environment and Education departments), 4 local primary and secondary schools (about 250 kids), Legambiente association.

DEL05 #2 • FishArt: “Let’s not wage war, let’s fight waste”

As part of the FishArt project agenda, transect walks and educational training initiatives have been combined in a major event, strongly requested by the local community. The synergy between local institutions and international research aims to stimulate civic participation on the problem of marine pollution and the care of the coastal territory. The event “Let’s not make war, let’s fight waste!” is a civic initiative promoted by the Extraordinary Commission supported by the Environment Area of the Municipality of Anzio which aims to involve all the components of civil society for a collaborative cleaning of the beaches, transforming the celebrations of the Anzio/ Nettuno landing into a moment of sharing and to raise awareness against marine pollution. On the occasion of the celebration of the 80th anniversary of the Anzio landing, volunteers and activists will be engaged in “community

plogging” (community cleanup) at the Lido dei Gigli public beach.

The initiative is organized by the European project New European Bauhaus “FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean at the Port of Anzio” led by the University of Turin and Sapienza University of Rome together with “Raw-News”, “PLATOON Cultural Development”, “Raw-Drivers” and with the support of the club Legambiente “Le Rondini” Anzio-Nettuno, in collaboration with the Extraordinary Commission supported by the Environment Area of the Municipality of Anzio. Federico Fornaro (Raw-News) took the lead in coordinating the logistic and the technical realisation. Press release available [here](#): - [Photos](#)

[FULL REPORT](#)

DEL05 #2 • FishArt: “Let’s not wage war, let’s fight waste”

Schoolchildren participating in the activity were awarded a **Eco Warrior "Certificate of Merit"** in recognition of their commitment to protecting the marine ecosystem.

Participants received a FishArt Project pin and each class was gifted a keychain in the shape of a Seahorse, made from recycled marine plastic collected in Anzio. The keychains are crafted by [Precious Plastic Torino](#), which has previously collaborated with the team on the **SeaPaCS** project.

CALL TO ACTION

DEL10 • “Plastisphere Explorations. Submarine plots of nature-culture” Geography Night

[photo: G. Lupinacci]

The International Night of Geography 2024 organized by La Sapienza University at the Botanical Garden of Rome, Largo Cristina di Sweden 23 A, from 8pm to 11pm the underwater photography exhibition “Explorations of the Plastisphere. Underwater plots of nature-culture” will be exhibited by photographer Giuseppe Lupinacci in collaboration with the British video-documentation agency Raw-News.

The exhibition presents the culmination of a collaborative research and documentation process aimed at making visible and reconceptualizing the presence of plastic in the oceans as an integral part of marine ecosystems.

The professional photographic documentation process was conducted in close connection with scholars of social geography and oceanography during the EU Horizon pilot project “SeaPaCS. Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution” (2023) and the EU-Culture Moves Europe project “Tentacular Thinking. Experiencing underwater assemblages of culture and nature” (2024), both led by Chiara Certomà (La Sapienza University of Rome).

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

DEL06 • FishArtEvent: Call for Collaboration & Artwork Creation

The EU NEB FishArt project invites creative citizens, innovators, activists, artists and change-makers individually or in associations (formal and informal), foundations, companies and institutions to propose initiatives to be implemented during the FishArt Event on 27 July 2024, from 6pm to 10pm at the Port of Anzio, Rome (Italy). The initiative is organized in collaboration with the European New European Bauhaus project “FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean at the Port of Anzio” led by the University of Turin and Sapienza University of Rome in collaboration with “Raw-News”, “PLATOON Cultural Development”, “Rawdrivers.org”.

The FishArt Event is an evening of collaborative experimentation and participatory art for the Ocean to support the redevelopment process of a vital public space for the city of Anzio, the Porto dei Anzio. The event will be held at the Molo Innocenziano. The active and creative participation of citizens is fundamental in order to best organize the event, and the FishArt team will avail itself of the advice of an international Scientific Committee which will consider all the proposals received. The synergy between local institutions and international research aims to stimulate civic participation on the problem of marine pollution and the care of the coastal territory. [FULL ARTICLE](#)

DEL05 • FishArt EU NEB COHORT SESSIONS

FishArt
Chiara Certoma'
What you do without using your job title!

📍 Anzio, Italy

1 FishArt participatory process supporting the requalification of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio, Italy.

2 FishArt aims to support and complement infrastructural requalification processes of the Fishermen's Harbour in the coastal city of Anzio (50,000 in., 60 km South of Rome, Italy) undertaken by the Local Administration via the realisation of a marine litter collection area. The FishArt participatory aesthetic and cultural transformation of the area is intended to revitalise a public space, functional for the local economy and closely connected with coastal waters, from the current state of dumping and degradation.

3 Fishermen, creative/ artistic communities

4 Building upon the local ecosystem analysis, the wide social network and the results of the recent EU project "SeaPaCS", FishArt envisages multi-stakeholder workshops with target groups (fishermen and artists cooperatives) and local stakeholders (administrations, students, associations, migrants, seagoing people, businesses and enterprises, scientists); multidisciplinary (social geography, oceanography, communication) and multi-sectorial (fisherman, artists, businesses) learning sessions; a Living Lab for co-design and realisation of artistic works and a final FishArt Event.

<https://crowdusg.net/fishart/>
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what are your strengths and super-powers as a team and project?

Our team is able to make change happen by mobilising multidisciplinary and radically participatory exploration, documentation and engagement techniques and informal tools to identify contexts-specific matters of concern and, by building on tacit competencies of local actors and multisectorial design skills, we turn these all into transformative knowledge for just sustainability

what are some upcoming challenges or team opportunities for growth?

Creating and operationalising a business plan for upscaling

May 2024: Remotely taking part in the EU NEB cohort session

<https://www.climate-kic.org/news/16-community-focused-projects-receive-new-european-bauhaus-funding>

DEL05 • FishArt LIVING LAB #2 Operative Meeting Berlin

16.05.2024 FishArt operative meeting with PLATOON and Raw-News companies in Berlin to discuss the broader impact of the project, meet creatives, and get inspired by Berlin's creative scene.

DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab: Mentorship program

21.05.2024 Meeting of the mentorship programme with [Oleg Koefoed](#) and [Vanessa Gerotto](#)

DEL07 • FishArt Event: Production meeting

03.06.2024 Operative meeting for preparing the in-person Living Lab with Fishermen and creatives

DEL07 • FishArt Event: Site Inspection

[photo M.Dato]

12.06.2024 Technical inspection by the FishArt team at Molo Innocenziano for FishArt Event preparation.

DEL07 • EVENT LOCATION SITE INSPECTION

DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab #2: Design Collaborative Process

29.04.2024 -30.05.2024 Living Lab activity #2: design of the collaborative art process (involving stakeholders) and preparation of artworks.

DEL05 #3 • FishArt Living Lab: Participants Meetup on Event Site

The FishArt Living Lab is held on the 29th June, in preparation for the FishArt Event on July 27th. This meeting is aimed at all of you who responded enthusiastically to our Call To Action by sending proposals and to the fishermen and representatives of local institutions.

Date: June 29, 2024

Time: 6pm

Location: Molo Innocenziano (in front of the hydrofoil boarding point) MAP

Purpose: Organisation of the FishArt Event on July 27th

Meeting Program:

- Presentation of the FISHART LIVING LAB Event Programme
- FishArt Museum of Marine Pollution: We will discuss how to set up nets from fishing for the Marine Trash Museum and the Fresh Trash Market performance.
- Presentation of the Projects Selected by the scientific commission.
- Organisation of workshops, creative laboratories and project arrangement.

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

DEL05 • LIVING LAB #3: PARTICIPANTS MEETUP AT CULTURE SEAPORT

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WHEN	WHAT	WHO	WHERE	ROLE	TYPE
01.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Project Management	MANAGEMENT
02.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Curator	PROGRAM
02.06.2024	MEETING RAW DRIVERS	Marcello, Francesca, Valeria, Vinz	Online	Curator	CURATION
03.06.2024	MEETING PLATOON	Marcello, Christoph Frank	Marquede	Event Production	PRODUCTION
06.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Sasha Perera	Berlin	Artist	PROGRAM
07.06.2024	MEETING SAFETY PLAN	Marcello, Stella	Berlin	Achitect	MANAGEMENT
09.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Cristiano Cesolari	Berlin	Artist	PROGRAM
10.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Francesca	Rome	Curator	MANAGEMENT
11.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Dadara	Online	Artist	PROGRAM
12.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Giuseppe Lupinacci	Molo Innocenziano	Artist	PROGRAM
12.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Fede, Emá, Marco, Kris, Vale, Giuseppe	Babylon Pizzeria	Construction	PRODUCTION
13.06.2024	LOCATION CHECK	Marcello, Fede, Emá	Molo Innocenziano	Construction	PRODUCTION
13.06.2024	MATERIAL & TOOLS	Marcello, Fede, Emá	Lega Navale	Construction	PRODUCTION
14.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Fede	Molo Innocenziano	Setup	PRODUCTION
15.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Fede, Emá, Valeria	Anzio House	Setup	PRODUCTION
16.06.2024	MEETING PRODUCTION	Marcello, Fede, Vale, Francesca, Biondo, Emá, Fulvio	Beach Meetup	Setup	PRODUCTION
16.06.2024	MEETING CURATION	Marcello, Raw Drivers	Ohana	Curator	PROGRAM
17.06.2024	MEETING COMUNE	Marcello, Monaco, Fede	Molo Innocenziano	Permits	MANAGEMENT
17.06.2024	PRODUCTION TASKS	Marcello, Marco, Krish, Fede, Emá	Anzio House	Sound System	PRODUCTION
17.06.2024	MEETING SUPPORTERS	Marcello, Pasquale SinEco, Marco D.	Romolo al Porto	Recycling	PRODUCTION
18.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Marco, Krish	Anzio House	Sound System	PRODUCTION
19.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Lucia Martino	Marinaretti	Coordinator	PRODUCTION
19.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Giuseppe Lupinacci & Fede	Fraschetta del Mare	Artist	PROGRAM
20.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, IBIS, Fede	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
20.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Ilaria Paccini	Molo Innocenziano	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING FISHERMEN	Angelo, Fede, Marcello	Molo Innocenziano	Fisherman	PRODUCTION
21.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Chiara	Online	Project Lead	MANAGEMENT
21.06.2024	TEAM MEETING	Marcello, Valeria, Fede	Beach Meetup	Setup	PRODUCTION
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Ilaria Acrobats	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Emaila Vocalist	Anzio House	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Alessandra di Cola - AlmaCreaz	Approdo	Artist	PROGRAM
21.06.2024	MEETING RAW DRIVERS	Marcello, Isa, Fede, Emá, Vale, Laura	Approdo	Curator	PROGRAM
22.06.2024	MEETING TECHNICIANS	Marcello, Marco, Cesare, Paolo	Anzio House	Sound Engineer	PRODUCTION
23.06.2024	MEETING MATERIALS	Marcello, Ema, Pasquale SinEco, Marcello,	SinEco	Recycling plant	PRODUCTION
24.06.2024	MEETING MANAGEMENT	Marcello, Chiara			REPORT
25.06.2024	MEETING COMUNE	Marcello			MANAGEMENT
26.06.2024	MEETING PARTICIPANTS	Marcello, Cristiano Cesolari	Lotoprod	Artist	PROGRAM
28.06.2024	MIDTERM REPORT	Marcello			MANAGEMENT
28.06.2024	DESIGN POSTERS	Marcello			PRODUCTION
30.06.2024	LIVING LAB	Legambiente, Con.Tatto, Uplishing, Raw Drivers, Dalia, Bianca, Roberto, Jester, Marcello, Chiara, Fede, Giuseppe		Participants	PROGRAM

DEL01 • MEETINGS & WORK SESSIONS

- [PROJECT MANAGEMENT WORKFLOW](#)
- [PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT](#)

List of meeting and work sessions leading up to the event serving to demonstrate the engagement of stakeholders and participants as well as partners and FishArt Team.

PROJECT ACTIVITY: JULY - OCTOBER

(See Annexes #2)

1. 08.07 • DEL10: FISHART EVENT INVITATION #1
2. 10.07 • DEL01: PRODUCTION MEETINGS & WORK SESSIONS
3. 23.07 • DEL010: FishArt Porto Cultura Program Announcement & Reminder #2
4. 26.07 • DEL07: FishArt Porto Cultura SetUp
5. 27.07 • DEL07: FishArt Porto Cultura Event
6. 04.08 • DEL08: POST EVENT REPORT: NEWSLETTER & SOCIAL MEDIA
7. 06.08 • DEL10: Raw-News Video Report Teaser: Event Photo & Press Release
8. 07.08 • DELEX: Pratiche di cittadinanza attiva per il mare di Anzio
9. 26.08 • DEL10: Raw-News Video Reportage
10. 12.09 • DEL05: FishArt Living Lab: Mentor Workshop
11. 20.10 • DEL04: FishArt Follow-Up Collab
12. 25.10 • DEL01: Follow-Up Collab Results Evaluation: Plan for the future Harbour
13. 30.10 • DEL11: Final Performance Activity Report

INTRO REPORT

Exploring the Intersection of Art, Science, and Community Engagement for Sustainable Marine Conservation

FishArt Porto Cultura, held on August 27th, 2024, at Porto di Anzio, serves as an innovative case study in the integration of participatory art and scientific communication within coastal communities. The event successfully engaged diverse stakeholders, including fishermen, institutions, local associations, artists, and active citizens, in a collaborative effort to celebrate and protect the ocean's cultural and ecological heritage. The report examines the principles and goals that guided FishArt, emphasizing inclusivity, sustainability, and interdisciplinary collaboration. By leveraging local expertise, cultural assets, and innovative artistic practices, FishArt transformed the Anzio Seaport into a vibrant cultural hub, raising awareness about marine conservation while fostering social cohesion. The report highlights the event's outcomes, including the promotion of sustainable

practices, the enhancement of art & science processes and the strengthening of community bonds. Furthermore, it discusses the possible transferability of the FishArt model as a blueprint for other coastal cities, as part of its sustainability and scalability plan, by proposing that participatory art can serve as a powerful tool for engaging communities in environmental stewardship. The findings highlight the importance of creative, community-driven approaches to addressing complex environmental challenges, offering valuable insights for future projects at the intersection of art, science, and civic participation.

FishArt serves as a compelling case study for how collaborative art practices can advance scientific understanding and foster sustainable solutions for ocean conservation. This report presents how participatory art models can facilitate multi stakeholder engagement, drive sustainable pathways, and offer insights into the broader implications for social and environmental change.

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DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

FishArt Porto Culture: A Triumph of Participation and Creativity at Port of Anzio

On Saturday 27 July, the Fishermen's Port of Anzio hosted the "FishArt Porto Cultura" event, an initiative that attracted over 200 participants including children, cultural and creative associations. The project, titled "FishArt. Participatory Art for the Ocean", used old fishing nets and waste collected by fishermen in the Mediterranean Sea to raise awareness of the need to create a shared ecological consciousness for marine conservation.

The day was a riot of creative and artistic activities, with workshops that allowed participants to express their creativity through clay sculptures, magnetic games, drawings and artefacts made with plastic recovered from the sea. The associations Legambiente, IBIS Onlus, Lega Navale Italiana Section of Anzio, Artalo Lab, Alterequo, Con.Tatto and UPublishing, together with many others, gave a fundamental contribution to the success of the event, transforming the port into a temporary space of co-creation. One of the most exciting moments was when the participants were able to observe the "Mare Dentro" sign hanging on the "Onda

Libera" stage, created by Allegra Guerrazzi, a symbol of the strong bond that unites the community of Anzio to the sea. Local fishermen, true guardians of the sea, shared their dreams of a clean sea, underlining the importance of closer collaboration with institutions for the creation of an ecological island for the collection of plastic waste covered by forms marine biological. With better resources at their disposal, they could be even more efficient in their work cleaning the sea, thus contributing to the health of marine ecosystems. The event highlighted the need to preserve not only the marine environment but also the professions and workers linked to the maritime world. Fishermen, shipyards, members of the naval league, young and old: everyone participated with enthusiasm, demonstrating a strong sense of belonging and commitment to the sea.

Program and featured artists

The event program was rich and varied, offering artistic exhibitions, co-creation workshops and cultural interventions. The artists presented evocative works that stimulated reflection on the relationship between man and the sea.

Artwork: Romolo Basili

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

Dadara exhibited a new installation entitled “Next Planet”, created using old fishing nets and waste found in the Mediterranean Sea. The work invites us to reflect on the relationship between man and nature and, if necessary, to ironically take the emergency exit to the next planet.

In the artist’s words: “ *The Mediterranean covers less than 1% of the global ocean, but is one of the largest sources of marine and coastal biodiversity on the planet. More than half a billion people live in the 21 countries that make up the Mediterranean region, which is home to more than 10,000 plant and animal species, nearly 30 percent of which are found nowhere else in the world. Like the rest of the ocean, the Mediterranean faces a number of serious threats, including overfishing, plastic pollution, climate change, ocean acidification and marine debris. Furthermore, the Mediterranean is warming 20% faster than the global ocean average due to climate change .*”

Romolo Basili presented sculptures of marine animals made from plastic bottles, underlining the seriousness of plastic pollution in the sea.

Artwork: Dadara

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

Ibis Onlus, represented by **Prof. Ferdinando Fornaro**, has created an installation that symbolizes the disorientation of fish trapped in the labyrinth of marine debris and has created the infrastructure of fishing nets to exhibit the works of all the creative laboratories, contributing in an consistent with the organization of the event.

Legambiente Circolo “Le Rondini” Anzio-Nettuno organized creative and educational activities for children, to promote awareness of marine and coastal pollution.

Bianca Simonetti of the Agarra La Onda

Photographic Studio exhibited works that combine food with objects that end up in our stomachs in the form of nano and micro plastics,

while **Giuseppe Lupinacci** presented artistic photographs documenting underwater life and the human impact on the ecosystem.

Laura Buffa of **Alterequo** exhibited “Plastocene”, a space to talk about the creative processes of transforming plastic waste into resources.

Artwork: Giuseppe Lupinacci

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

ALmaCreaz exhibited unique creations made with materials found on the beaches of Anzio, which came to life on fishermen's nets.

Artalo Lab proposed a critical reflection on the interaction between living organisms and plastic in the form of a human fetus that creates a metal mesh in the shape of a mother,

and **Roberta Fucci** presented an interactive illustration with magnets to raise awareness about separate waste collection and cleaning the seas.

Ilaria Paccini addressed the topic of invasive alien species with a work on oxidised aluminium,

while **CON TATTO & UPublishing** organised fairy tale listening and drawing workshops for children, and a Character Design workshop for young creatives, promoting creative recycling, the exchange of book-crossing readings and the love of the sea.

Dalia Valdez organised clay art creations with children and adults, raising awareness of issues related to marine pollution.

Artwork: AlmaCreaz

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

Officina delle Memorie with **Francesca Ciardi**, Leen Ekman , **Amiar Souphiene** , **Olivia Fornaro** and **Valeria Schinzari**, attracted large crowds, including local poets, with its narratives and symbolic practices that convey collective memories.

Project Documentation

Jimlea Nadezhda Mendoza presented a scientific research: ” *The knowledge of fishermen’s plants in the Venice Lagoon of Italy and in the Lagoon Lake of the Philippines* ” by the **Biocultural Diversity Lab, Ca Foscari University of Venice**.

Simone and Fulvio, from the **PERDITEMPO 3** fishing vessel, have launched their **ECO-FISHING** campaign where they will document their sustainable short-range fishing practices following the ancient traditions of the Fishermen of Anzio, handed down from Father to Son.

Performance: Officina delle Memorie

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

Allegra Guerrazzi created a series of signs to indicate the demarcation of spaces, with mottos such as: Onda Libera, Mare Dentro, Marine Trash Museum, Fresh Trash Market

ONDA LIBERA SOUND SYSTEM • SEA IN with **Joe Vangeli** (Giovanni Evangelista), a true connoisseur who created the perfect atmosphere for the daytime program.

Marold Langer-Philippsen has created sound installations with marine themes that explore the evolution of the sea. Together with an unprecedented Live of marine sounds created in situ by our **Onda Libera Sound Crew**.

Music: JoeVangeli DJ

Artwork: Alterequo

Artwork: Allegra Guerrazzi

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DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

With musical introduction by **Emaila Kangudie**, who played Redemption Song, The event soon reached its climax with the sunset DJ set by **Perera Elsewhere**, a magical moment in which the artist's genre-busting music resonated across the harbour.

During one of the most splendid sunsets in Anzio, people danced wearing the wonderful masks of fish and creatures from the deep sea created by **Allegra Guerrazzi**, giving life to a sort of tribal dance. This regeneration ritual was a good omen for the Port of Anzio, which deserves to be a public place lived in and loved by citizens.

Music: Emaila Kangudie

Music: Perera Elsewhere

Artwork: Allegra Guerrazzi

DEL07 • FishArt Culture Seaport: REPORT

Lotoprod – **Cristiano Cesolari** showed multimedia installations on the impact of marine pollution by activating a series of light installations that interacted with music.

Artwork: Lotoprod

Molo 5.63
Banqueting - Eventi

Piazzale Marinai d'Italia

Piazzale Marinai d'

FISHNET ARTMAZE

LO CHE TIRI A MARE, POI TE LO MAGNI!!!

Marine Trash Museum

ZONA CALMA
DEFLUSSO

ONDA
LIBERA
STAGE

LIVING LAB
MAKER TABLE

BACKSTAGE / STORAGE

ADDETTO
ESTINTORI

SICUREZZA

ZONA CALMA
DEFLUSSO

30m x 15m = 450 m²

Mercato PescePlastica
FRESH TRASH MARKET

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Eni

Molo 5.63
Banqueting - Eventi

Piazzale Marina d'Italia

Piazzale Marina d'Italia

Eni

ZONA CALMA
DEFLUSSO

Marine Trash Museum

BACKSTAGE / STORAGE

ADDETTO
ESTINTORI

ONDA
LIBERA
STAGE

LIVING LAB
MAKER TABLE

OPEN WALL

ZONA CALMA
DEFLUSSO

30m x 15m = 450 m²

Mercato PescePlastica

FRESH TRASH MARKET

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DEL EXTRA • Active citizenship practices for the sea of Anzio

MERCOLEDÌ 7 AGOSTO 2024, ORE 19.00

Via delle Robinie 76, 00042 Anzio

Pratiche di cittadinanza attiva per il mare di Anzio

Interventi

- **La campagna Goletta Verde: monitoraggio delle acque**
Circolo Legambiente "Le Rondini" di Anzio e Nettuno
- **Ricerche, documentazione e partecipazione sulla costa di Anzio**
Chiara Certomà (Università di Roma La Sapienza)
- **Ricerche, documentazione e partecipazione sulla costa di Anzio**
Federico Fornaro (Lega Navale Italiana - Anzio)

Proiezione dei video

- **SeaPacs: Participatory Citizen Science against Marine Pollution**
(RAW-News/Università Torino)
- **Non facciamo la guerra, combattiamo i rifiuti**
(RAW-News/Università Roma)

**evento riservato ai soci del CNC*

“Active Citizenship for Anzio Sea” - FishArt team presented project results at the Cincinnato Nautical Circle in collaboration with local environmental and cultural associations.

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DEL05 • FishArt Living Lab: Mentorship program #2

12.09.2024 Workshop part of the mentorship programme with [Oleg Koefoed](#) and [Vanessa Gerotto](#)

OLEG PRESENTATION

2. Overall progress of the project

2.4. Achievement of the objectives

DEL10: Visual products

DEL08: Web Communication

Management of communication, networking and dissemination [UniTo, sup: media-agency] (Ob3-5, m.1-10, CL01).

Set up and maintenance of web page, social media, mailing list;

Networking local stakeholders+target groups (fishermen and artists) and international experts, in-site communication;

Media contacts; photo and video documentation; scientific paper elaboration.

D: 1 web page, 6 newsletters, 6 press realises, 1 scientific paper, 2 photo exhibitions (25 professional pictures) and 3 professional videos (2/3 mins), 6 YouTube videos. O:C Ou:1

ARTE PARTECIPATIVA PER L'OCEANO

21 MAR • 6pm

FISHART

CO-LABORATORIO

LEGA NAVALE ITALIANA DI ANZIO

Riviera Zanardelli 28 Anzio - Roma

Photo: Giuseppe Lupinacci / Raw-News

ARTE PARTECIPATIVA PER L'OCEANO

10 MAGGIO 2024 • 9:30 - 12:30 Lido dei Gigli
**NON FACCIAMO LA GUERRA
COMBATTIAMO I
RIFIUTI!**

DEL10 • “FISHART PORTO CULTURA PHOTO REPORTAGE

[photo: G. Lupinacci]

A selection of professional photos by Giuseppe Lupinacci directed by Raw-News. The vivid pictures make the event come to life and convey the participatory essence of the FishArt Porto cultura event

[EVENT PHOTOS](#)

DEL10 • "FISHART PORTO CULTURA PHOTO REPORTAGE"

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DEL10 • “FISHART PORTO CULTURA VIDEO REPORTAGE

[photo: G. Lupinacci]

We are pleased to present the Video Reportage, produced by the independent video documentation agency Raw-News, of the FishArt Porto Cultura event held on July 27, 2024, at the port of Anzio. This event is an extraordinary example of how civic participation can unite art and science to promote environmental sustainability. Involving fishermen, local institutions, artists, and citizens, the event demonstrated how art can raise awareness of marine issues and inspire concrete actions for ocean conservation.

Believing that it is essential to understand the relationship between society and the Ocean to adopt sustainable management and behaviour models, the FishArt project, aligned with the United Nations' "One Ocean" perspective and the European

Commission's "Restore our Ocean and waters by 2030" Mission, is helping to raise awareness of the link between the health of the global ocean and its role in supporting the Earth's vital ecological cycles.

The FishArt project, in continuity with the civic research activities on marine pollution conducted during the previous European SeaPaCS project (documented in the Raw-News video), uses art and participatory creativity tools in the belief that participation can foster a deeper emotional connection with the environment.

[FULL ARTICLE](#)

FISHART PORTO CULTURA

TEASER

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FISHART PORTO CULTURA

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DELO8 • FISHART EVENT COMMUNICATION E-FLYERS & GIF

DELO8 • FISHART EVENT COMMUNICATION E-FLYERS & POSTERS

DEL08 • FishArt Newsletter Campaigns

Totale iscritti alle email

312 -- rispetto all'ultimo anno

Crescita netta totale delle iscrizioni

0.00% -- rispetto all'ultimo anno

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 INVITATION](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 REPORT](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #1 VIDEO REPORT](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 CALL TO ACTION](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 REPORT](#)

[LIVING LAB #2 VIDEO REPORT](#)

[LIVING LAB #3](#)

[OPEN CALL FOR ARTWORK CREATION](#)

[FISHART EVENT INVITATION #1](#)

[FISHART EVENT INVITATION #2 \(PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT\)](#)

[FISHART PORTO CULTURA REPORT \(TEASER\)](#)

[RAW-NEWS VIDEO REPORTAGE](#)

[FISHART FOLLOW-UP COLLAB](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #2 INVITATION](#)

[CO-LABORATORIUM #2 REPORT](#)

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DEL08 • Web Communication Products

Communication channels opened on Instagram, YouTube and Project Homepage:

<https://crowdusg.net/fishart/>

<https://www.instagram.com/fisharteu/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@FISHARTEU>

Affiliated channels by Project Partners

https://www.instagram.com/platoon_alliance/

<https://www.instagram.com/rawdrivers/>

<https://www.instagram.com/DADARA>

3. Overall management process, challenges faced and risk mitigation

3.1. Overall management process

3.2. Risk register review and mitigation plan

3.3. Unexpected challenges during project implementation

3.4. Role of partners involved and their integration into the project's implementation

3.5. Project changes

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.1. Overall management process

Project Management Structures and Procedures have been conducted by Laura Corazza jointly with Chiara Certomà (thanks to a collaboration agreement with the University of Rome Sapienza where Certomà moved just after the starting of FishArt project), Certomà, whose competence guarantees a smooth management plan implementation. She had been co-adjuvanted by Paolo Di Martino in all managerial, administrative and logistic activities and by a part-time junior research assistant (hired on Corazza funds NOT connected to any other project and NOT included in this NEB call budget). Workshops (T03, 04 and 06) and participatory education and training are realised via the engagement of fishermen coops, Platoon and Raw-News and local admins to realise FishArt activities and deliver quality outcomes timely. Multiple representatives of all social groups (including marginalised ones are involved. FishArt team organised Living Lab (T05) in collaboration with target groups and local stakeholders. International multidisciplinary, multi-sectorial colleagues expressed their interest in contributing to on-site events.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.2. Risk register review and mitigation plan

Risk Management and Contingency Plan

Risk Category	Risk Title	Risk Likelihood	Risk Impact	Risk Description	Risk Mitigation
EXTERNAL	Practical difficulties in the <u>realisation</u> of artworks	2	3	Practical <u>difficulties</u> in the <u>realisation</u> of artworks (lack of necessary material, technical issues connected with the feasibility of planned artworks, logistic issues <u>connected</u> with the installation of artworks in specific areas of the Harbour).	The practical, <u>organizational and logistic</u> risks connected with the <u>realisation</u> of the artworks are <u>mitigated</u> by preliminary elaborating in the Living Lab a "plan B". This requires the design of two different versions of the agreed-upon artworks that envisage different practical arrangements so that the second version can substitute at an early stage of preparation in case of envisaged difficulties.
OPERATIONAL	Scarce participation	2	4	Scarce participation of citizens <u>to</u> the planned public events (workshops, co-training <u>and</u> FishArt Event).	Preventive measures include massive <u>communication effort</u> before the events, including social media/traditional media/ <u>in place</u> advertisements. As there are no possibility to remedy at a later <u>stage</u> , an individual invitation will be sent to all potential interested subjects well in advance.

OPERATIONAL	Problems with target groups participation	1	4	Difficulty of securing <u>participation</u> of target groups in the Living Lab (fishermen and artists cooperatives).	Networking with relevant subjects in advance can prevent the occurrence of this risk. Should the risk occur, cognate cooperatives will be contacted.
OTHER	Low social acceptance	1	4	Social acceptance of the artistic revival of the Harbour by citizens, i.e. adverse socio-political context. <u>In consideration</u> of the success of the previous "SeaPaCS" project in Anzio and the high and wide participation in the initiatives, it is extremely unrealistic that FishArt is not receiving an enthusiastic welcome.	The support and active engagement of the local administration, i.e. Anzio City Council (notably the support of Director of the Environment and Public Space Department) will further boost FishArt realisation. We will prevent this by preliminary <u>face-to-face informal meeting and invitation</u> to all the local stakeholders and by <u>mobilizing</u> our media contacts for <u>creating</u> a favourable context.
OTHER	Difficulty of publishing research results	2	1	Difficulty of publishing research results in selected outlets (after the conclusion of FishArt).	Preventive measures include: preliminary consideration of the most appropriate reviews; draft versions of the papers discussed with colleagues and supervisor; experts will be asked to read and provide suggestions for improvement; proof-reading. Should the difficulties persist, alternative outlets will be considered.
STRATEGIC	Difficulties in securing support for next years	3	2	Difficulty in securing financial support for next years' edition of the FishArt.	We already have established contact with private business (e.g. D'Eramo Imballaggi, Servizi Marittimi Anzio) willing to support the next editions. However, to prevent this risk we will engage local businesses (shops, museums, restaurants, production plants...) in the organisation of <u>next</u> editions of the FishArt Event.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.3. Unexpected challenges during project implementation

Compared to the envisaged risk, none occurred except the last: difficulties in securing support for the coming years. This is partly due to the fact that the technical committee has been dissolved and elections are currently underway. Nonetheless, some of the civic groups that participated, as documented in the follow-up plan, are willing to continue.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.4. Role of partners involved and their integration into the project's implementation

Stakeholders at Anzio Seaport: A Brief Insight & Analytical Report

Introduction

Anzio Seaport, with its rich maritime history and cultural heritage, is a hub of various stakeholders, each contributing uniquely to its dynamic environment. This report provides a detailed analysis of the stakeholders at Anzio Seaport, their connections, and the essential nature of their collaboration. Special emphasis is placed on finding strategies to engage the younger generation with professions related to maritime culture and developing an ecological consciousness.

Fishermen and Maritime Workers

Angelo Grillo, President of the Fishermen's Union, represents the interests of local fishermen, mostly long-range Trawling Fishing. He was present at the first Collaboratorium and helped us liaise with different fishermen. Through him we met **Manuele** while he was repairing a fishing net. A veteran fisherman who shared with us historical anecdotes about biologists visiting every four years to study nanoplastics in fish brains, which he believes originate from household washing machines and textile discharges. **Marcello Audace**, a long-range trawling captain, has provided us with fishing nets for the event and various forms of support, playing a crucial role in the operational aspects and setup of the FishArt Porto Cultura. The **Corto Raggio** (short-range) fishermen, **Simone and Fulvio** from the fishing boat Perditempo 3, are innovators working on a new sea-cleaning project that incorporates live streaming and a civic observatory for citizen science.

Their work exemplifies the blend of traditional practices and modern technology. **Gianluca**, a young captain, symbolizes the generational shift in maritime professions. He relies heavily on technology but faces criticism from the older guard for lacking practical decision-making skills essential in risky situations.

Challenges and Required Solutions

A sense of belonging and recognition is vital for the community. One pressing issue is the decommissioning of the community-led oil tank initiative without a replacement. Additionally, the **strabordo attracco**—a ready-made docking solution—remains unused due to restrictions imposed by the Capitaneria di Porto. **Ecological islands** to recycle and dispose of marine plastics and trash found at sea, a solution desired by all stakeholders, face coordination challenges. All stakeholders have started working together for a common cause, and although they hold different opinions and motivations, they are pushing in the same direction.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.4. Role of partners involved and their integration into the project's implementation

Key Collaborators and Support Systems

LEGAMBIENTE has been the most supportive association and it really helped having them on board as collaborator, they bring along a long term reputation which gave us an edge with other institutions. At the seaport we had few good tips from **Marco Palomba**, a connector within the cooperative for fish auctions, provides essential water supplies and connects the team with behind-the-scenes workers at the seaport. The **Cantiere Navale**, represented by **Gianpaolo Gallinari Maestro d'Ascia**, a master boat builder, highlights the declining client base and reputation of Anzio's naval yards. Investing in marine trades and excellence is critical for attracting newcomers. Despite financial struggles, Maestro d'Ascia supported the event with high-voltage electricity.

Lega Navale Italiana, the association secretary **Francesca**, emphasizes the need for enthusiastic teenagers to discover sailing and sea culture. Numbers are declining every year.. Many local young people lack interest in learning how to sail, which is a significant concern for the preservation of maritime heritage.

Municipal and Coastal Authorities

The **Comune di Anzio**, particularly the Environment Office led by **Eugenio Monaco**, has been pivotal in securing permits and navigating bureaucratic challenges. The **Demanio Marittimo**, represented by **Bruno**, offered valuable advice to avoid bureaucratic backlash. The **Capitaneria di Porto**, under **Maresciallo Constabile**, has been professional and instrumental in preparing the event space. Although the **Guardia Costiera** did not engage actively, they were kept informed.

Commercial Small Business and Hospitality Sector

Local businesses have been generally supportive of the cause. The Boat Fuel Distributor, owned by **Alberto Vecchiarelli** and operated by **Angelo Luca**, offered facilities for power and logistics. The **Bar del Porto** and **Compact One Bar** granted permission to post event information and supported the initiative. Renowned restaurants like **Capolei**, **Lampara (Cittolo)**, and **Fraschetta del Mare** have also endorsed the FishArt cause.

Beach Bathing Establishments

Local beach bathing establishments under concession, notably **Stabilimento Balneare "La Quiete"** at Marinaretti Beach, have also played an important role. They provided full support for finding young volunteers, focusing on engaging individuals in their early twenties. The involvement of "Stabilimenti Balneari" is pivotal for activating a new generation in maritime and coastal activities.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.4. Role of partners involved and their integration into the project's implementation

Schools and Associations

Since the first "collaboratorium," we have been in touch with several local associations such as Legambiente, Ibis Onlus, Con.Tatto, and UPublishing. Together with some of these organizations, we organized a Beach Cleanup with the support of the Comune di Anzio's Environment Department, headed by Eugenio Monaco. The Beach-Head cleanup action symbolizes a different way to commemorate the Anzio Beach-Head, a horrific battle in the Second World War that caused the loss of many young lives and remains a vivid memory among Anzio citizens.

The plogging action, titled "**Let's Not Make War, Let's Fight Waste!**" took place on the 10th of May and was a great success. It saw the participation of three schools: "**Falcone, Collodi and Acqua del Turco**", with 200 students and teachers, together with eco-activists from **Legambiente Circolo Le Rondini Anzio-Nettuno**. The local association **Raw Drivers** helped us coordinate the action and involve the schools on very short notice.

I've been told that kids who participated still play the "Eco-Warrior" game on the beach. Instead of building sandcastles, they prefer picking up waste, although it should not be their duty. Nonetheless, it works very well because adults who see them cleaning become more aware and ashamed of their behaviour, making them more likely to clean up the beach after themselves.

FishArt Porto Cultura: Exploring the Sea Through Art

FishArt Porto Cultura at the Anzio Fishing Port embarks on an artistic journey exploring various perspectives of the sea and its cultural significance. This initiative aims to raise ecological awareness and inspire a deep connection with maritime traditions. Through art, the project highlights the importance of marine conservation and the impact of pollution, fostering a sense of responsibility and stewardship among visitors.

3. Overall management process and risk mitigation

3.5. Project changes

Work Plan Modification

- T04_3. Public meeting with local schools presenting works on the society's attachment to the sea in Anzio and marine waste.)
→ realised during the LADI & the Sea event and for the Community Beach Plogging Action with schools and 200 students.
- T06_6. Change the description in "T. 03 Fist workshop. Kick-off plenary open meeting..." into "T. . 03 Kick-off meeting ..." and the description in "Task 06 Second workshops [UniTo] (Ob4, m.10, CL01). Plenary open meeting..." into "Task 06

4. Achievements and impacts

- 4.1. *Status of the achievement of the outputs, outcomes and KPIs compared to the project workplan*
- 4.2. *Impact of activity on target group, public space etc.*
- 4.3. *Impact of activity on local policies: feedback from local authorities and impact on their strategy*

4.1 Final Status of the achievement of the outputs, outcomes and KPIs

KPI code and name	KPI description	KPI Target value	Your contribution	Current progress (%)
KSN02	Demonstration/pilots/living labs within a project that actively involve citizens and/or local associations	200	Living Lab Sessions, Community Plogging with schools, Fishermen and citizens	Current progress (100%)
EITHE08.1	Participants in (non-degree) education and training	1	Community involvement with participation of schools, Fishermen and citizens	Current progress (100%)
CL01	Strengthened resilience to the unavoidable impacts of climate change	40	Marine Pollution sensibilisation and marine conservation divulgation	Current progress (100%)

LIST OF OUTCOMES & KPI

KPI Code	KPI Name	Description	Target Value	Achievement	Supporting Evidence	Remarks
KSN02	Demonstration/Pilots/ Living Labs	Living Labs actively involving citizens and associations through participatory art and cleanup initiatives.	200 Participants	100% Achieved	Beach Cleanup Report, Living Lab Attendance Records	Focused on co-design activities and promoted actionable environmental awareness through engagement.
EITHE08.1	Education & Training Participation	Non-degree educational sessions involving schools, citizens, and fishermen on marine conservation.	1 Event	100% Achieved	Co-training Reports, School Workshop Documentation	Educational programs successfully engaged local schools and provided interactive learning experiences.
CL01	Strengthened Climate Resilience	Marine pollution sensitization through Living Labs, art events, and awareness campaigns involving local actors.	40 Actions	100% Achieved	Reports on Beach Cleanup, Event Documentation	Actions included workshops, cleanup drives, Living Labs, and collaborative awareness-raising campaigns.
COM01	Communication Products	Development of communication materials (reports, newsletters, press releases) to highlight project impact.	6 Products	100% Achieved	Communication Products Archive	Successfully shared project progress, outputs, and achievements with stakeholders and the public.

LIST OF DELIVERABLES

Deliverable Code	Name of Document	Description	Status	Supporting Evidence	Remarks
DEL 01	Management Plans	Administrative, managerial, risk, and ethical compliance plans for FishArt activities.	Completed	Management Plan PDF	Outlines the structure and workflow for effective execution of FishArt activities.
DEL 02	Plan for the Future Harbour	Prepared during the kick-off plenary meeting with stakeholders, outlining process design and proposals for enhancing public space sustainability.	Completed	Plan Document PDF	Incorporates scenario-building insights and community recommendations for Anzio's harbor.
DEL 03	Financial Plan	A financial roadmap for participatory education, training initiatives, Living Lab setup, and the FishArt Event logistics.	Completed	Financial Plan PDF	Budget allocation ensured the successful delivery of all key activities.
DEL 04	Mid-Term Report	Intermediate report detailing project progress, achievements, stakeholder engagement, and identified risks.	Completed	Mid-Term Report PDF	Provided accountability for project progress midway and allowed adjustments as needed.
DEL 05	Co-Training Events	Three co-training events: Transect walk with fishermen, workshops on ocean challenges, and public presentation with schools on marine waste.	Completed	Reports, Photos, Event Details	Delivered successfully with active participation from schools, fishermen, and local stakeholders.
DEL 06	Artworks	Collaborative art installations and performances co-designed in the Living Lab, focusing on marine pollution and sustainability.	Completed	Photos, Art Design Process, Event Logs	Highlighted marine waste issues while engaging the public through creativity and collaboration.
DEL 07	FishArt Event	Final FishArt exhibition at the Fishermen's Harbour featuring three art installations/performances with public participation and engagement.	Completed	Event Photos, Video Documentation	Successfully achieved public engagement goals and promoted sustainability through participatory art.
DEL 08	Web Communication Products	Development of a project webpage, newsletters (6 issues), and press releases (6), ensuring public outreach and engagement.	Completed	Webpage Link, Newsletter Archive, Press Releases	Ensured visibility and widespread dissemination of project activities and achievements.
DEL 09	Visual Products	Two photo exhibitions (25 images each), three professional videos (2–3 mins), and six YouTube videos documenting project activities and outcomes.	Completed	Photo Exhibitions, Video Reports, YouTube Links	Successfully showcased FishArt's impact and raised awareness on marine conservation.
DEL 10	Follow-Up Plan	Report on results and future steps, including the scaling-up plan based on stakeholder collaboration and recommendations for the Anzio port.	Completed	Final Report with Follow-Up Strategy PDF	Provides a structured roadmap for scaling the project, ensuring long-term benefits for the local community.
DEL EXTRA	Active Citizenship Practices Report	Community-driven activities such as "Beach Cleanup" and follow-up collaborations, showcasing citizen involvement and actionable environmental care.	Completed	Event Logs, Beach Cleanup Report, Stakeholder Testimonials	Demonstrated strong community participation and measurable environmental impact.

CLO1: 40 distinct marine pollution sensibilisation and marine conservation divulgation activities.

Specific Actions Under CL01:

1. **Living Lab sessions** with the local community, involving interactive discussions and activities on marine pollution.
2. **Community Beach Plogging:** Schools, fishermen, and citizens participated in beach cleanup activities.
3. **Transect Walks:** Guided walks with fishermen to explore and raise awareness of pollution issues in the harbor area.
4. **Educational workshops:** Collaboration with local schools to train 200 students on marine waste management.
5. **Collaborative art events:** Art installations at the harbor showcasing marine conservation themes.
6. **Public exhibitions:** Display of photographs and sculptures made of waste materials.
7. **Educational film screenings** on marine ecosystems and pollution.
8. **Workshops for upcycling marine waste** (fishing nets, plastics) into art and functional items.
9. **Training sessions for fishermen** on the environmental impact of polystyrene crates and solutions such as DUWO reusable crates.
10. **Installation of ecological islands:** Discussion and proposals for recycling stations for waste collected at sea.
11. **Media campaigns** to raise awareness about marine plastic pollution.
12. **Mentorship workshops** with experts, including Oleg Koefoed and Vanessa Gerotto, to co-develop climate resilience strategies.
13. **"Let's Not Make War, Let's Fight Waste!" campaign:** A civic initiative to clean beaches and raise awareness during the 80th Anzio Beach-Head anniversary.
14. **Interactive art workshops for children** to teach them about marine pollution.
15. **Miro Board ideation sessions:** Collaborative brainstorming sessions to create future scenarios for Anzio harbor.
16. **Civic mobilization events** involving citizens in marine waste reporting and data collection.
17. **Stakeholder dialogue sessions:** Negotiations between local institutions, fishermen, and citizens on harbor cleanliness and waste reduction.
18. **Awareness posters and newsletters** distributed locally to highlight marine conservation topics.
19. **Reusable crate pilot program** to reduce polystyrene usage in fisheries.
20. **Creation of FishArt Keychains:** Seahorse-shaped keychains made of recycled marine plastic to promote waste recycling.
21. **"Eco Warrior Certificates"** for students who participated in waste collection.
22. **Collaborative fish market improvement proposals** to create a clean and accessible market.
23. **FishArt Follow-Up Collaboratorium:** Brainstorming for future actions and projects in Anzio.
24. **Photographic installations** showcasing the impacts of marine debris on sea life.
25. **Digital storytelling** to document the environmental history of Anzio's port and engage a broader audience.
26. **Community surveys** to assess public attitudes toward marine pollution.
27. **Policy recommendations** to local government based on FishArt findings.
28. **Floating waste collection trials:** Discussion of floating systems to collect harbor waste.
29. **Student competitions** for creative solutions to reduce marine litter.
30. **Interactive games and activities** for children to teach recycling and conservation.
31. **Media partnerships** for regional and national coverage of FishArt activities.
32. **Storytelling exhibitions** combining art and data to communicate climate change impacts.
33. **Data collection and visualizations** to showcase marine waste statistics.
34. **Interactive sculptures:** Proposals for "plastic-eating" sea monster installations that collect waste.
35. **Follow-up reports** and proposals for local authorities and stakeholders.
36. **Community Artwork** depicting marine life and pollution impacts.
37. **Temporary Porto Cultura Lab** setup for community-led climate resilience ideas.
38. **Workshops with artisans** to upcycle materials like discarded sails and fishing nets.
39. **FishArt Festivals:** Multi-sensory events involving art, and education on marine conservation.
40. **Evaluation of waste impact:** Quantification of the amount of marine trash collected by local fishing fleets.

4.1 Work plan status vs proposed work plan

FishArt GANTT Chart

Tasks/months	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01. Activity Management	D1		D8							
02. Communication and networking	D8	D10	D8	D10	D8, 10	D10	D8	D10	D8, 10	D8, 9, 10
03. Fist workshop		D2,3 M								
04. Participatory education and training initiatives				D5	D4,5	D5 M				
05. FishArt Living Lab and Event									D6,7	M
06 Second workshop										D11 M
<i>M (milestones), D (deliverable)</i>										

4. Achievements and impact

4.2. Impact of activity on target group, public space etc.- *Ideation process to co-create solutions for the most pressing challenges -*

Ecosystem questions

MAPPING

Who are the stakeholders that benefit the most from FishArt - now and in the near future? -

Who are the stakeholders that contribute the most to FishArt - now and in the near future? -

What are the most important locations in the bigger area that FishArt operates in, where is the Heart?

How does the ecosystem live, where does its force come from?

4. Achievements and impact

4.2. Ideation process to co-create solutions for the most pressing challenges

MENTOR WORKSHOP SESSION: MAPPING FISHART MIRO BOARD

R.A.C.I Map - for FISH ART 2024

RESPONSIBLE - Doing the work - the core team, generally

ACCOUNTABLE - Answers for the work - often leadership

CONSULTED - Experts/SMEs to learn from

INFORMED - Kept in the loop

Stakeholders

fill names into the sticky notes and place them in the circles

Markers

- Decision Maker
- Heavy Influencer
- [Double click to add another]

4. Achievements and impact

4.3. Impact of the activity; describing potential impact on local policies: feedback from local authorities and impact on their strategy

Interdisciplinary Collaboration: The event fostered a unique mode of working that brought together artists, scientists, fishermen and community members in a collaborative process. This interdisciplinary approach has led to more impactful outcomes, demonstrating the value of integrating diverse perspectives in addressing complex issues.

Community-Driven Art: Unlike traditional art events, which are often artist-led, FishArt was driven by the community, with local participants playing a central role in shaping the event's content and direction. This participatory approach ensured that the event was deeply rooted in the local context and resonated with the community's values and concerns.

Cultural and Ecological Assets: The event drew upon the missing cultural and ecological resources of the Anzio Seaport, using the physical space of the port as a canvas for artistic expression and scientific exploration while denouncing the ecological issues

Potential impact on local policies: feedback from local authorities and impact on their strategy

One of the mayoral candidates for the upcoming elections contacted us in early November. He and his party indicated alignment with local policymakers. However, we chose not to engage further to avoid any potential conflict of interest during the election campaign, particularly given that the local council had been under administration for the past two years due to mafia infiltration.

5. Conclusions, lessons learnt and recommendations

5.1. Lessons learnt

Lesson learnt & recommendations

The most important lesson learnt was the importance of engaging the younger generation in maritime professions and traditions, it resulted to be crucial for the sustainability of Anzio's maritime culture and the development of a common vision for the Anzio Seaport. FishArt Porto Cultura plays a vital role in this by integrating various strategies:

- 1. Educational Programs:** Developing partnerships with local schools to incorporate maritime history, marine pollution, and practical skills into the curriculum.
- 2. Youth Workshops:** Organising workshops and hands-on activities where young people can learn about boat building, navigation, fishing techniques, and marine conservation practices.
- 3. Mentorship Programs:** Pairing experienced fishermen and maritime workers with young apprentices to pass on traditional knowledge, skills, and ecological awareness.
- 4. Interactive Exhibits:** Creating a series of interactive exhibits and Living Labs at the seaport to attract and educate visitors about maritime professions and the importance of marine conservation.
- 5. Digital Engagement:** Utilizing social media and digital platforms to share stories, interviews, and behind-the-scenes looks at maritime life, making it more accessible and appealing to tech-savvy youth.

Conclusions

Small investments and coordinated efforts, potentially supervised by an external watchdog agency, could ensure transparency and drive results. The stakeholders of Anzio Seaport are united by a profound knowledge and passion for the sea. They are custodians of Anzio's maritime culture and are pivotal for transforming the seaport into a social space that fosters citizen participation and the development of sea-related trades and traditions. Engaging the younger generation in these professions is crucial for preserving and advancing this rich cultural heritage. The FishArt Porto Cultura initiative contributed to raise ecological awareness, fostering a deeper connection with the maritime environment through art and community engagement. Stakeholders at this stage only need a sign of recognition and someone to lead by example.

ANTTIUM
URBS ARTIS

PORTO D'ANZIO VISION

RESULTS OF THE WORKSHOP TO IMAGINE THE FUTURE OF THE PORT OF ANZIO

5. Conclusion, lessons learnt and recommendations

5.2. Recommendations for the replication and/or upscaling up of the realized activity

CO-LABORATORIUM #2

Summary of Results from the Follow-Up Collaboratorium October 20, 2024

The “[Follow-Up Collaboratorium](#)” event was held on October 20, 2024, at the [Lega Navale Italiana di Anzio](#) as the final event of the “[FishArt. Arte Partecipativa per l’Oceano al Porto di Anzio](#)” project. This project was funded by the [New European Bauhaus](#) and led by the [Università degli studi di Torino](#) and [Università La Sapienza di Roma](#) - Dipartimento [MEMOTEF](#), in collaboration with [Raw-News](#), [Raw Drivers](#) and [Platoon Cultural Development](#). With endorsement and support of [Comune di Anzio](#).

The event brought together citizens, port operators, associations, and local institutional representatives for a discussion on the **future of the Molo Innocenziano** and surrounding areas. The objective was to explore visions that would elevate the port, transforming it into a lively, welcoming, and sustainable environment— a truly **Public Space**.

The opening session was led by Chiara Certomà, who presented the project's key results ([PDF slides available](#)), followed by Federico Fornaro’s introduction of the [video reportage](#). Marcello Dato then initiated a discussion on [future proposals for the port](#), featuring scenario-building concepts developed in collaboration with mentors Oleg Koefoed and Vanessa Gerotto from the European Commission. This work will inform the creation of a final follow-up document for the Municipality and citizens of Anzio.

The event included representatives from schools, fishing cooperatives, environmental associations, artists, and marine industry professionals.

[See Annexes](#)

INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

Proposals and Inspirations from Living Lab Meetings

The following proposals emerged during various Living Lab meetings, where ideas for a shared vision of the future of Anzio Port as a public space were discussed. The FishArt project laid the groundwork for networks and collaborations with various local stakeholders, who came together to propose different potential scenarios that can inspire local authorities.

The **FishArt Porto Cultura** project represents the natural evolution of the journey that began in 2023 with **SeaPaCS**, "**Participatory Science Against Marine Pollution**." Recently, SeaPaCS won the **Diversity & Collaboration Award at the European Citizen Science Prize 2024 at Ars Electronica**, for promoting sustainable solutions at the Port of Anzio.

This project has expanded through initiatives such as **Tentacular Thinking** and **L.A.D.I & The Sea**, which have explored new forms of artistic representation and environmental awareness. Tentacular Thinking, piloted in Berlin, introduced innovative methods of photographic exhibitions related to the sea, while L.A.D.I & The Sea addressed climate change by involving artists and researchers in an interdisciplinary approach.

With the summer participatory art event, **FishArt Porto Cultura**, the project now aims to consolidate the actions already undertaken by developing a sustainable, replicable, and scalable system.

PRECONDITIONS FOR FUTURE ACTIONS

Upscaling Recommendations:

Before launching new initiatives, it is essential to enhance the basic conditions of the port area—a regulated economic space critical to local fishermen, traders, and operators.

Ensuring a clean, well-managed environment, beneficial not only for those who work there but also for citizens and visitors, is key to sustaining the continuity of the interventions already undertaken.

Any future project must start from this foundation to avoid operating in a degraded context. One of the main findings of the SeaPaCS project

highlighted the urgent need to phase out the highly polluting polystyrene fish crates and replace them with DUWO crates, equipped with traceable chips.

This project focuses on implementing a circular system for the return and tracking of reusable fish crates, in addition to **establishing port recycling stations for the waste collected at sea**, involving fishermen, traders, and local institutions.

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB POPOSALS

SCENARIO BUILDING WORKSHOP

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #1

1. Port Infrastructure and Public Spaces Optimization of Existing Resources:

One of the central points has been to improve the management of port infrastructure, particularly regarding the Molo Innocenziano, including waste management, maintenance of the piers, and optimizing the management of the seabed and parking for vessels. (The dredging of Molo Pamphili was mentioned, which currently does not allow participation in important regattas.)

Public and Meeting Spaces:

Participants envisioned scenic walks where citizens and tourists can relax, enjoy the landscape, and experience the port not just as a transit area, but

as a social space. Although laws mandate that the port must remain completely free for economic activities related to fishing and trade, it would be desirable for the port to also be a true public space, complete with restrooms, benches, and urban gardens, while of course not hindering the commercial and logistical activities related to the fishing economy.

Beautiful and Clean Fish Market: "Like in Valencia!" exclaimed some participants, proposing the creation of an accessible, beautiful, and clean fish market. This could become a landmark for promoting the culture of local fish and fostering a closer bond between citizens and fishing activities.

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #2

2. The **Porto Cultura Lab** aims to be a temporary space for dynamic and creative research, serving as the **operational center of the project**.

The container, modularly furnished with fish crates, is equipped to host: **exhibitions, debates, workshops, screenings, and participatory artistic installations.**

The proposal to create a space dedicated to the project aims to involve fishermen, citizens, restaurateurs, and traders in the **transition from the use of polystyrene boxes to a sustainable system of reusable crates.**

The goal is to engage the local community by combining science, art, and social innovation.

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #2

Porto Cultura Lab: Project Activities and Impact

The Porto Cultura Lab will also serve as a collection and distribution point for reusable fish crates, where the washing process will be tested in **collaboration with the local cooperative.**

The aim is to create a practical and sustainable reuse model that also generates economic savings for fishermen and industry operators. A study is planned to determine how much could be saved by using the circular system with reusable crates instead of polystyrene ones.

Main activities in the container:

- Artistic and photographic exhibitions
- Debates and meetings with fishermen, environmental experts, and citizens
- Screenings of films and documentaries about the sea and sustainability
- Participatory workshops and community actions for adults and children

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #3

3. Art and Awareness

Although the main focus of the project is technical and environmental, the artistic aspect remains a central component for raising community awareness. The plastic fish crates will also be used as modular elements to furnish the space in front of the container, transforming into chairs and tables for hosting events, exhibitions, and workshops.

Raw Drivers presents: “[MOSTRA MARINA: Found at Sea](#)”

An "experiential" photography exhibition will take place in the shallow waters near the ancient Villa of Nero, on the beach of Anzio. A 4-meter-high structure made from sailing masts will rise from the water, supporting long fishing nets as canvases. Large-format photographs by [Giuseppe Lupinacci](#) depicting waves and underwater life, documented with the help of fishermen off the coast of Anzio, will be displayed on these nets. Visitors, with their feet in the water, will be able to walk around the installation at sunset.

Concept: rawdrivers.org

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #3

Cultural, Artistic, and Educational Initiatives

FishArt: There was discussion about reproducing the FishArt event, perhaps in a smaller version managed by local schools, with creative activities related to the sea and a dedicated children's area. A small themed playground was also proposed in some designated and safe zones where no dangerous equipment is left.

Sculptures of "Plastic-Eating Sea Monsters": A very evocative proposal involves creating metal sculptures depicting sea monsters designed to "eat" plastic. These "monsters" would serve as collectors for marine debris, where citizens and fishermen could deposit plastic found in the sea or on the beach. A regular emptying system would be necessary, but the idea has the potential to transform the cleaning of the port and beaches into a creative and participatory activity.

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FISHART PLASTIC EATING SEA MONSTERS #3

Local business and cultural associations can support the production of FishArt Beach Plastic Eaters by donating materials and financing the production. Their logo would be displayed on a commemorative plaque.

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #3

Permanent Installations and Porto

Cultura Lab: In addition to the sculptures, the creation of permanent artistic installations and temporary research workshops, like the Porto Cultura Lab, has been envisioned. These would focus on projects centered around the sea and the port. This initiative would not only give a new cultural meaning to the port space but also serve as a meeting point for fishermen, citizens, and researchers, promoting dialogue and innovation in environmental and artistic fields.

Educational Tours: Another interesting proposal is to organize educational paths on the pier for families and children, focusing on both the beauty of the sea and its fragility. These “Art Walks,” enhanced by photographic installations and educational information, would raise visitors' awareness of marine pollution and microplastics.

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #4

4. Environmental Awareness and Circular Economy

- **Ecological Island and Marine Waste Collection:** A particularly pressing issue is the creation of an Ecological Island dedicated exclusively to the collection and disposal of waste recovered from the sea by local fishermen. The discussion focused on the problem of marine waste that requires specialised treatment through the establishment of a supply chain within the territory of Anzio. A well-organised ecological island would allow for the effective treatment of this waste, promoting a circular economy and engaging the local community.

- **Disposal of Used Oil:** The urgency of equipping the port with an efficient system for disposing of used oil produced by fishing vessels was also emphasised. This system would ensure proper management of waste generated by fishing activities, reducing the risk of pollution and accidental oil spills into the sea.

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #4

Quantification of Marine Waste:

The importance of measuring how much marine waste is collected by the fishing fleet of Anzio was discussed. One possible initiative would be to dedicate a special day, such as “**World Trash Day**,” to raise public awareness by showcasing data on the amounts of plastic and waste collected each month. This could help highlight the impact of marine litter on the health of our sea.

Promotion of Maritime Trades:

Participants expressed a desire to promote skills related to maritime trades by integrating educational programs that can train new generations while also encouraging sustainable development of the port, in line with the European Commission’s “Blue Growth” guidelines.

- Precious Plastic Upcycling

PRECIOUS PLASTIC COLLAB

User-oriented integrated service for 3D printing environments using materials recycled from marine plastic waste.

Tolling

Plastic Recycling Hub can deliver tolling services for manufacturers who are looking to reuse or re-purpose of plastic offcuts or any type of purgings.

Identification and quantification of microplastics

Creations made from marine plastic waste collected in Anzio. Public Furniture: Urban Bench

PRECIOUS PLASTIC COLLAB

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #5

5. Governance and Community Participation

- **Participatory and Transparent Management:** One of the most pressing topics was the shared and transparent management of the port. There was discussion about the need to maintain constant dialogue between the municipal administration, fishermen, and other

local stakeholders to ensure that decisions are aimed at preserving the entire port of Anzio, both in its commercial and recreational areas, as well as all coastal areas as a common good and thus public property.

FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #5

Future of the Port of Anzio:

The uncertainty surrounding the fate of the port area of Anzio, following the bankruptcy of the Capo d'Anzio company, has raised concerns among participants and a clear indication of the preference for the port space to be entirely publicly managed and used. Participants proposed creating a

coalition of public stakeholders (fishermen, traders, and associations) along with the public concessionaires united to defend the port as a common good.

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FOLLOW UP COLLAB • PROPOSAL #6

Laura Buffa's "Blue Carpet" concept for Anzio proposes an ethical fashion show where garments are crafted from marine-recovered materials—like torn Finn sails, beached umbrellas, and discarded fishing nets—to create an "Anzio Ethical Capsule." This unique fashion capsule would actively involve local seamstresses, sailmakers, and other artisans in the production process, making it both a community-centered and environmentally conscious initiative. Buffa envisions the project as part of the next FishArt festival, ideally with a moderate but feasible budget.

The "**Blue Wave**" Fashion Show aims to raise community awareness on sustainability in the fashion industry, a sector known to be the third most polluting industry worldwide, contributing significantly to ocean pollution with an estimated 14 million tons of microplastics annually. Through collections created in collaboration with local designers and artisans, the project seeks to merge art, fashion, and marine conservation, encouraging participants to reflect on their environmental impact, particularly on marine ecosystems.

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CONCLUSIONS:

FishArt presents itself as a *proof of concept* of the ability of participatory art to promote cultural, social, and environmental change.

The project focused primarily on the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, local engagement, and creative expression in addressing the complex issues faced by coastal communities today.

FishArt offers a replicable and scalable model for how art and science can come together to create significant impacts on society and the environment.

The proposals from the workshop, although purely inspirational, reflect the desires of citizens, associations, and port operators.

The results will remain accessible to citizens and the administration of the municipality of Anzio as a source of inspiration to initiate a dialogue and a shared path with citizens aimed at maintaining a clean, inviting, functional, and inclusive space.

FISHART
SUSTAINABILITY
STEPS

1

PROJECT
ACTIVATION
2024

1

2

ISOLE
ECOLOGICHE
PORTUALI

2

3

PORTO CULTURA
LAB
2025

3

4

4

CREATIVE
SCIENCE LAB
2026

6. Use of Resources

Describe the total budget consumption in 2024 of the participating partners per cost category and explain any deviations from the work plan (i.e., if budget consumption has been higher or lower than the original total budget planned in 2024 for a particular cost category).

Cost Category	Budget in EUR (original budget from all participating partners from PLAZA)	Reported Costs in EUR (total costs from all participating partners)	Description of Reported Costs and justification of deviation if any
1.Personnel	9,981.00 €		
2.Subcontracting	.00 €		
C1. Travel and Subsistence	500.00 €		
C2. Equipment	.00 €		
C3.Other goods, works and services	9,500.00 €		
D1.Financial Support to Third Parties	.00 €		
D2.Internally invoiced goods and services	.00 €		
E.Indirect costs (25% of A+C1+C2+C3)	4,993.00 €		[E. INDIRECT COSTS] do not require a justification
TOTAL	24,974.00 €		

7. Annexes

1. [Project Activity #1](#)
2. [Project Activity #2](#)
3. [Porto d'Anzio Vision](#) - Sustainability Plan & Upscaling proposed by stakeholders
4. [BEACH CLEANUP ACTION](#)
5. [VIDEO TEASER](#)
6. [FISHART EVENT VIDEO REPORT](#)
7. [EVENT PHOTOS](#)
8. [PROGRAM](#)
9. [EVENT TECHNICAL SETUP](#)
10. [FOLLOW UP COLLABORATORIUM](#)
11. [POSTERS & FLYERS](#)
12. [INSTAGRAM](#)
13. [YOUTUBE CHANNEL](#)

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Marcello Dato is a Cultural Producer who served as Project Manager for "*FishArt: Participatory Art for the Ocean*," a forward-thinking initiative supported by the **New European Bauhaus** and undertaken through a research scholarship with the **University of Turin**.

Working closely with a dedicated team, including **Chiara Certomà**, **Laura Corazza**, and **Federico Fornaro**, Marcello played a pivotal role in coordinating the project's diverse facets, from organizing the event to liaising with local stakeholders and ensuring the smooth execution of the final stages.

Marcello curated and organised the contributions of artists, scientists, and the Anzio community. His efforts contributed to making *FishArt* a living demonstration of

how participatory art can drive environmental awareness and community engagement.

Marcello's role encompassed production, coordination, and detailed reporting of outcomes, emphasising teamwork, creativity, and shared vision.

His contributions reflect the project's commitment to fostering inclusive spaces where art, science, and local voices converge to inspire future sustainability initiatives.

BENEFICIARY:

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO

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COLLABORATORS:

RAW-NEWS
report around the world

PLATOON

CULTURAL
DEVELOPMENT

**RAW
DRIVERS**

Con il Patrocinio di:

Città di Anzio

**2021
2030** United Nations Decade
of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

DIPARTIMENTO DI METODI E MODELLI
PER L'ECONOMIA IL TERRITORIO E LA FINANZA
MEMOTEF

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA